

Experimental and Computational Insights of Schiff Base Copper(II) Complexes of Para-Substituted Benzaldehydes towards some Bacterial and Target Proteins

Interactions

 Conventional Hydrogen Bond

 Carbon Hydrogen Bond

 Pi-Pi Stacked

 Pi-Alkyl

S1: Ampicillin-4YRD

Interactions

- | | |
|----------------------------|-----------|
| Attractive Charge | Pi-Sulfur |
| Conventional Hydrogen Bond | Alkyl |
| Carbon Hydrogen Bond | Pi-Alkyl |
| Pi-Sigma | |

S2: F1-4YRD

Interactions

- | | |
|-------------------|----------|
| Attractive Charge | Alkyl |
| Pi-Sulfur | Pi-Alkyl |

S3: F2-4YRD

Interactions

- | | |
|----------------------------|-----------|
| Attractive Charge | Pi-Sulfur |
| Conventional Hydrogen Bond | Pi-Alkyl |
| Pi-Sigma | |

S4: F3-4yrd

S5: F1-Cu-4YRD

S6: F2-Cu-4YRD

S7: F3-Cu-4YRD

S8: Ampicillin-6KJ6-F

Interactions

 Conventional Hydrogen Bond

 Pi-Sulfur

 Pi-Alkyl

S9: Ampicillin-6KJ6-J

Interactions

- Conventional Hydrogen Bond
- Carbon Hydrogen Bond
- Pi-Cation

- Pi-Pi Stacked
- Pi-Pi T-shaped
- Pi-Alkyl

S10: F1-6KJ6-F

Interactions

 Conventional Hydrogen Bond

 Pi-Cation

 Pi-Sigma

 Pi-Pi Stacked

 Pi-Alkyl

S11: F1-6KJ6-J

S12: F2-6KJ6-F

S13: F2-6KJ6-J

Interactions

- Conventional Hydrogen Bond
- Pi-Cation

- Pi-Pi Stacked

S14: F3-6KJ6-F

Interactions

- Conventional Hydrogen Bond
- Pi-Cation
- Pi-Sigma

- Pi-Pi Stacked
- Pi-Alkyl

S15: F3-6KJ6-J

S16: F1-Cu-6KJ6-F

S17: F1-Cu-6KJ6-J

S18: F2-Cu-6KJ6-F

S19: F2-Cu-6KJ6-J

S21: F3-Cu-6KJ6-J

Interactions

 Conventional Hydrogen Bond

 Pi-Alkyl

BLU Carbon Hydrogen Bond

S22: Ampicillin-6p8o

Interactions

- Conventional Hydrogen Bond
- Pi-Pi Stacked

- Alkyl
- Pi-Alkyl

S23: F1-6P8O

Interactions

- | | | | |
|---|----------------------------|---|----------|
| | Alkyl |
| | Pi-Alkyl |
| | Pi-Pi Stacked | | |

S24: F2-6P8O

Interactions

 Conventional Hydrogen Bond

 Pi-Pi T-shaped

 Pi-Alkyl

S25: F3-6P80

S26: F1-Cu-6P8O

27: F2-Cu-6P8O

S28: F3-Cu-6P8O

Interactions

 Conventional Hydrogen Bond

 Pi-Alkyl

S29: Ampicillin-4OSG

Interactions

 Conventional Hydrogen Bond

 Pi-Alkyl

S30: F1-4OSG

S31: F3-4OSG

S33: F2-Cu-4OSG

S34: F3-Cu-4OSG